

Multi-fold Gravity can Violate P-Symmetry. It is Aligned With Observations of Asymmetry of the Orientation of Tetrahedra of Galaxies

Stephane H. Maes¹

December 10, 2022

Abstract

A few papers have reported the observation of galaxy asymmetries: when drawing oriented tetrahedrons between galaxies, the left and right oriented distributions are skewed. It seems the reflection of a parity symmetry breaking across the universe. If true, it is considered that it may require New Physics fields, or particles, to explain these observations. It is consistent with earlier work investigating if the CMB, and its polarization, could present Parity symmetry violations. These were conjectured to related to a new field present before inflation, or to the behavior of the quintessence.

However, there may be more fundamental mechanisms to justify parity asymmetries, like the result of spacetime orientation by 4D gravity, or gravity itself not always respecting parity symmetry. The former is encountered in the multi-fold electroweak symmetry breaking, when gravity orients spacetime, and the latter is a fundamental property of the multi-fold mechanisms, and multi-fold gravity.

Radiated right-handed virtual neutrinos involved in multi-fold gravity are, now unable to interact via the weak interaction, and hoping to hide with the Higgs, which impacts propagation, and therefore the long range massive gravity effects, from when involving left-handed neutrinos. It is a first explanation for parity symmetry violation by gravity.

As a results fluctuations, or even larger structures, which are parity images of each other, do not feel gravity effects the same way, nor produce the same gravity effects, even if the difference is small. With inflation and expansion, these effects can become apparent macroscopically and cosmologically. Therefore, the distributions of such structures, like oriented tetrahedra, could differ, as reported to be observed. No need to involve New Physics, in the sense of a new field, or the presence of quintessence, one just needs to consider and include gravity.

The most important conclusions is that the multi-fold theory predicted such a P-symmetry breaking in its original paper, and, by now, there may have been observations of such behaviors at cosmological scales, and with tis paper explanation for them. These are additional hints in favor of the multi-fold theory, and how it may apply to our real universe.

1. Introduction

In a multi-fold universe [1,8-10,22], gravity emerges from entanglement through the multi-fold mechanisms. As a result, gravity-like effects appear in between entangled particles [1,24,25], whether they be real or virtual. Long range, massless gravity results from entanglement of massless virtual particles [1,26]. Entanglement of massive virtual particles leads to massive gravity contributions at very small scales [1,27]. It

¹ shmaes.physics@gmail.com

is at the base of the E/G Conjecture [24], and the main characteristics of the multi-fold theory [22]. The multi-folds mechanisms also lead to a spacetime, which is discrete [1,65], with a random walk fractal structure [1,62], and non-commutative geometry [1,62,65,80,108,139], that is Lorentz invariant [1,10,23,65,136,143], and where spacetime nodes and particles can be modeled with microscopic black holes [1,4]. All these recover General Relativity (GR) at large scales, and semi-classical models remain valid till smaller scales than usually expected. Gravity can therefore be added to the Standard Model (SM) resulting into what we define as SM_G : the SM with gravity effects non-negligible at its scales. This can contribute to resolving several open issues with the Standard Model and the Standard Cosmological Model without new Physics other than gravity [1,4-60,62-65,70-145]. These considerations hint at an even stronger relationship between gravity and the Standard Model, as finally shown in [23,111].

Note added on December 29, 2023: In this paper, references in italic were added on December 29, 2023.

Among the multi-fold SM_G discoveries, the apparition of an-always in-flight, and hence non-interacting, right-handed neutrinos, coupled to the Higgs boson is quite notable [1,35,42,47,65,114]. It is supposedly always around the Higgs boson, and it is due to chirality flips by gravity of the massless Weyl fermions, induced by 7D space time matter induction and scattering models, and hidden behind the Higgs boson or field at the entry points and exit points of the multi-folds [1,4,23,29,33-37,65,80,111]. Massless Higgs bosons modeled as minimal microscopic black holes mark concretized spacetime locations [14]. They can condensate into Dirac maxwell Kerr-Newman soliton Qballs to produce massive and charged particles [1,4], thereby providing a microscopic explanation for a Higgs driven inflation, the electroweak symmetry breaking, the Higgs mechanism, the mass acquisition and the chirality of fermions and spacetime; all resulting from the multi-fold gravity electroweak symmetry breaking [35]. Above the energies of the multi-fold gravity electroweak symmetry breaking, massless particles are induced by the patterns of the massless bosons walks. The multi-fold theory has also concrete implications on New Physics like supersymmetry, superstrings, M-theory and Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) [1,8-21,72,83,129,139].

Multi-folds are encountered in GR at Planck scales [5,6] and in Quantum Mechanics² (QM) if different suitable quantum reference frames (QRFs) are to be equivalent relatively to entangled, coherent or correlated systems [7]. This shows that GR and QM are different facets of something that they cannot well model: multi-folds [1,52,93,97].

We start the paper with a short review of multi-fold gravity [1] that results from the entanglement of virtual particles, and include massive and massless contributions [1,24-26,106], as well as gravity-like effect due to entanglement of real particles [1,24,25,132,133,143].

Then, we discuss how gravity ensures the existence of right-handed neutrinos, always in flights in the multi-folds, and behind Higgs bosons, and their role in enabling traversability of wormholes to implement the multi-folds [1,42,47,63], and as a dilaton responsible of the 2D random walks [1,6,52,107], gravity effects [106] and stabilization the Kaluza Klein induction mechanisms of the 7D multi-fold space time matter induction, along with the multi-fold mechanisms kinematics and dynamics [114,136].

The next steps involve discussing spacetime orientation as part of the gravity electroweak symmetry breaking [4,33-35,37], and how multi-fold mechanisms can break Parity [1], and have the effects amplified to cosmological scales by inflation and expansion. Although, how parity transformation exactly applies on multi-fold gravity may be subject to different scenarios, they seem to imply some level of P-symmetry violation. We explain two mechanisms, there may be others.

² Standing in for Quantum Physics in general.

Recent papers report observations of asymmetries between left-handed and right-handed tetrahedra drawn among a compilation of known galaxies [66-68]. [69] had putatively anticipated examples of P-violations in the polarization of the CMB, based on a new field present before or during inflation, or quintessence.

In this paper, we can motivate what these observations reflect, if indeed correct. Interestingly, we do not need to introduce a separate field that would be new, or the quintessence, something not really encountered so far in our multi-fold models of inflation, spacetime with positive cosmological constant [1,15,27,32,139], Ultimate Unification (UU) [1,28-30], and the 2D regime of gravity [1,16,35,53,62,64,65,106], and not aligned with our prediction of a desert for new fundamental particles above the energies of the (multi-fold gravity) electroweak symmetry breaking energy scales [1,30]. Indeed, with gravity violating P-symmetry, we do not need additional mechanisms to have asymmetric distributions of orientations / parity of sets of galaxies. They are simply the result of the amplification of such parity violations, which handle differently left or right handed perturbations. Of course, one could question if patterns of relative positions of galaxies carry meaningful orientation. But then again, the observed left and right-handed distributions should then be balanced if they weren't carrying meaningful orientations, and [66-68] show that it is not the case.

2. Multi-fold Gravity

[1] proposes multi-fold universes built on a few principles, including the apparition of multi-fold mechanisms between entangled systems [1,8-10,22,24,25,125,131,132,135,144]. Multi-folds can be traversed by some paths of the path integral, which instantaneously ties the systems. When computing the impact on the path integrals of such mechanisms, a gravity-like attractive effective potential appears. With masses or energy sources emitting pairs of entangled virtual particles, this model recovers gravity, the equivalence principle [1,38], and General Relativity (GR) [1,6], and the SM, including with gravity effects non negligible at its scales, i.e., the SM_G . massive virtual particles lead to massive gravity contribution [1,26], mostly at the scale of the short ranges of these particles, except for the contributions of the neutrinos that are also long ranged, and not really detectable and distinguishable from the massless contributions from photons.

These contributions, add without in general impacting the recovered GR, except again at the SM_G scales.

In this model, gravitons are not physical [1,52,70,71,106]. They live in the tangent dual $AdS(5)$ as the multi-folds attached to entangled particles, and at best should be considered as quasi particles [1,52,71,106].

3. Multi-fold gravity, Right-handed neutrinos and Higgs bosons

A consequence of the multi-fold approach is that GR remains valid, even if adjusted for massive contributions at classical but also semi classical or way smaller scales, and its effects are non-negligible at the scales of the SM (see the references provided in section 1).

In particular, spacetime orientation [37], and chirality flips due to gravity [1,37] imply the existence of massive right-handed neutrinos, and their anti-particles, not observed because they are always in-flight, and/or hidden behind Higgs bosons at entry, exit and mapping points within the multi-folds [1,32,42,47,63,65,136]. Their presence could allow GR based multi-folds implementations by traversable wormholes [1,63,136].

Spacetime orientation is behind how SM particles, including chiral ones, are space time matter induced and scattered from the 7D embedding space [4,23,29,33,34,35,37,111].

This model may also contribute to explaining the matter antimatter asymmetry [46].

4. Multi-fold P-symmetry breaking

Note added on December 29, 2023: This section has been somewhat clarified on December 29, 2023.

Conventionally, it is known that neutrinos interact only through the weak interaction that maximally violates the parity symmetry. Parity is not a conserved constant of motion for the neutrinos even if it is Lorentz invariant [146]. It is just not a good quantum number in anything involving neutrinos.

At energies below the gravity electroweak symmetry breaking, the right-handed neutrino is part of an isospin doublet with the (massive) Higgs boson [35]. This is what we explain with the right-handed neutrino being hidden in the multi-folds behind the Higgs boson.

The gravity flip of chirality can be modeled with the following new symbolic Lagrangian contributions:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Grav}} = (v_R \quad f(\text{Gravity})) \begin{pmatrix} (\rho+v) \\ \sqrt{2} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \nu_L + \text{h.c.} + (g(\text{Gravity}) \quad \nu_L) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ (\rho+v) \\ \sqrt{2} \end{pmatrix} \nu_R + \text{h.c} \quad (1)$$

The first term of (1) involves the Higgs boson field, and the sea of Higgs in the vev (vacuum expectation value), while the second term involves the conjugate doublet: the Higgs anti particle field, which is the same Higgs boson with a different contribution of the sea of Higgs in the vev. See [61] for example. The sea of Higgs in the vev absorbs any change in Y_w (Weak hypercharge) and T_3 (Weak isospin).

In (1), $f(\text{Gravity})$, describes the impact in the gravity field. Per [106], and its JT / dilaton gravity analysis, this amount to impact on the Higgs boson, recovering the isospin doublet of [35], that indicates that the right-handed neutrino (and its anti-particle) stays along associated to the Higgs boson. $g(\text{Gravity})$ refers to another contribution to gravity that we take as also including the effects of Higgs associated to the multi-folds when multi-folds deactivate.

Note also that when a left-handed neutrino propagates, it is subject to other interactions. When a right handed neutrino propagates, it does not interact with anything, except for gravity flips and with the Higgs, but will opportunistically aim to seek refuge behind/around a Higgs boson. Therefore, the propagation also differs between the two chirality, and violates parity (neutrinos are typically propagating at $\sim c$). Yet virtual neutrino contribute to long range gravity [1]. This is a second contribution to parity violation by gravity.

Above the energy scales of the electroweak symmetry breaking, parity can still be flipped by gravity [1,42]. Therefore, gravity is not P-symmetric.

With (1), we see that gravity effects are impacted by parity changes. Above are some of the contributions to the P-violation by multi-fold gravity.

Note that so far, as we mentioned, everybody knew by now that the weak and hence electroweak interaction violates Parity. However, there was not simple explanation on how it affected gravity and spacetime. We now have such proposed mechanism. There may be more.

5. Observed orientation asymmetry for tetrahedra of Galaxies

[66] popularizes a summary of the latest papers [67,68] who report the observations of asymmetries of the orientation of tetrahedral drawn between galaxies in the sky. [66-68] claim that the observed asymmetries are statistically significant, and the two papers seem to confirm such conclusions.

These works, and proposals to explain the observations, were inspired by [69] that suggested looking for parity violation in the CMB polarization. All these works also suggest New Physics with proposal to introduce additional fields during inflation or invoking quintessence.

6. No need for New Physics

Considering our results in terms of the Ultimate Unification (UU) [1,28,29,106], and prediction of a desert of new fundamental particles above the electroweak scales [1,30,50], and the fact that we did not need quintessence for inflation [1,27,32], or to justify superstrings [15], we are a bit skeptic of just New Physics explanations [30,47-50].

With the (1) in section 4, there is no need for New Physics, other than:

- the real universe being multi-fold, something hinted by [1,5-7] (required here), and more generally [1,4-60,62-65,70-145].
- gravity effects are not negligible at the scale of the SM, leading to SM_G (required only in terms of the role played to introduce right-handed neutrinos) [1].

And so, instead of involving new fields or quintessence, we argue that, if confirmed, this galaxy asymmetry is explained by the P-symmetry breaking property of multi-fold gravity. Indeed the P-violation of gravity implies P-asymmetry of spacetime, or, said differently, perturbations, which can be considered as parity change versions of each other, may not evolve the same way. When amplified by inflation and expansions, the effect can be seen at macroscopic or at cosmological scales, just as say for (multi) fractal effects [1,62].

Note that, conventionally, while we could equally propose that (1) can apply, it is not really considered because gravity is typically considered as negligible for the SM, they do not have multi-fold mechanisms which introduce the additional contributions to the Lagrangian met when flipping by gravity right-handed neutrinos, and they do not consider the Higgs / right-handed neutrino isospin doublet; heck in general they do not have a right-handed neutrino.

7. Conclusions

The paper repeats and clarifies how multi-fold gravity can violate parity, because of the right-handed neutrino contributions. We do not claim that other effects may not also contribute. It clarifies that topic with respect of [1], where we did not have all the details worked out. It is original in the sense that, while parity violation by the weak / electroweak symmetry breaking is well known, there was no clear explanation on how it would impact gravity and spacetime.

We interpret the reported observation of asymmetry of the orientation of tetrahedra of galaxies as explained by multi-fold gravity, instead of other New Physics. We also take it as another indication in favor of the multi-fold theory, and the fact that our real universe may be multi-fold.

References

- [1]: Stephane H. Maes, (2020-2022) "Quantum Gravity Emergence from Entanglement in a Multi-Fold Universe", HIJ, Vol 2, No 4, pp 136-219, Dec 2022, <https://doi.org/10.55672/hij2022pp136-219>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/09/paper-published-as-preprint-quantum-gravity-emergence-from-entanglement-in-a-multi-fold-universe/>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/11/09/quantum-gravity-emergence-from-entanglement-in-a-multi-fold-universe-2/>, and [viXra:2006.0088](https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.0088), (June 9, 2020). Errata/improvements/latest updates at <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7792911>.
- [2]: Wikipedia, "Reissner–Nordström metric", https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reissner%E2%80%93Nordstr%C3%B6m_metric. Retrieved on March 21, 2020.
- [3]: Wikipedia, "Kerr–Newman metric", https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kerr-Newman_metric. Retrieved on March 21, 2020.
- [4]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), "More on Multi-fold Particles as Microscopic Black Holes with Higgs Regularizing Extremality and Singularities", [viXra:2210.0004v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.0004v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/02/28/more-on-multi-fold-particles-as-microscopic-black-holes-with-higgs-regularizing-extremality-and-singularities/>, February 25, 2021.
- [5]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Multi-folds, The Fruit From The Loops? Fixing "Oops for The Loops" May Encounter Multi-folds in General Relativity And The E/G Conjecture", [viXra:2212.0206v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2212.0206v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/12/31/multi-folds-the-fruit-from-the-loops-fixing-oops-for-loops-encounters-multi-folds-and-the-e-g-conjecturein-general-relativity/>, January 1, 2022.
- [6]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "Deriving the Multi-fold Theory from General Relativity at Planck scale", [viXra:2302.0129v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.0129v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/02/22/deriving-the-multi-fold-theory-from-general-relativity-at-planck-scale/>, February 22, 2022.
- [7]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "From Quantum Relational Equivalence to Multi-folds Encounter in the Real Universe and Confirmation of the E/G conjecture", [viXra:2302.0108v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.0108v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/02/12/from-quantum-relational-equivalence-to-multi-folds-encounter-in-the-real-universe-and-confirmation-of-the-e-g-conjecture/>, February 7, 2022.
- [8]: Stephane Maes, (2020-2023), "Web Site Tracking all Publications around the Multi-fold universe", Navigation page listing all papers, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/shmaes-physics-site-navigation/>.
- [9]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), "The Multi-fold Theory: A synopsis", [viXra:2112.0144v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2112.0144v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/12/24/the-multi-fold-theory-a-synopsis-so-far-v2-end-of-2021/>, December 24, 2021. Note that additional links will always be available at <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/05/03/the-multi-fold-theory-a-synopsis-so-far/> to track the latest and interim versions of the synopsis, as they may be published under different title or URL/publication numbers.
- [10]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "Understanding the Multi-fold theory principles and the SM_G", [osf.io/xc74t](https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.0154v1), https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/03/11/understanding-the-multi-fold-theory-principles-and-the-sm_g/, March 11, 2022. Also as Stephane H Maes, (2022), "A tutorial on the Multi-fold theory principles and the SM_G", [viXra:2303.0154v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.0154v1), https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/blog-2/a-tutorial-on-the-multi-fold-theory-principles-and-the-sm_g/, March 11, 2022.

- [11]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), "Comment on LQG, Superstrings, Supersymmetry and most GUTs/TOEs, all have big problems exposed by the Multi-fold Theory", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/12/27/the-multi-fold-theory-a-synopsis/#comment-3293>. Published on January 9, 2022.
- [12]: Stephane H. Maes, (2020), "Comment on why no supersymmetry", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/10/11/circular-arguments-in-string-and-superstring-theory-from-a-multi-fold-universe-perspective/#comment-934>. Published on October 12, 2020.
- [13]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Renormalization and Asymptotic Safety of Gravity in a Multi-Fold Universe: More Tracking of the Standard Model at the Cost of Supersymmetries, GUTs and Superstrings", [viXra:2102.0137v1, https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/09/19/renormalization-and-asymptotic-safety-of-gravity-in-a-multi-fold-universe-more-tracking-of-the-standard-model-at-the-cost-of-supersymmetries-guts-and-superstrings/](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/09/19/renormalization-and-asymptotic-safety-of-gravity-in-a-multi-fold-universe-more-tracking-of-the-standard-model-at-the-cost-of-supersymmetries-guts-and-superstrings/), September 18, 2020.
- [14]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Circular Arguments in String and Superstring Theory from a Multi-fold Universe Perspective", [viXra:2103.0195v1, https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/10/11/circular-arguments-in-string-and-superstring-theory-from-a-multi-fold-universe-perspective/](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/10/11/circular-arguments-in-string-and-superstring-theory-from-a-multi-fold-universe-perspective/), October 5, 2020.
- [15]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), "The String Swampland and de Sitter Vacua: A Consistent Perspective for Superstrings and Multi-fold Universes", [viXra:2208.0078v1, https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/01/12/the-string-swampland-and-de-sitter-vacua-a-consistent-perspective-for-superstrings-and-multi-fold-universes/](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/01/12/the-string-swampland-and-de-sitter-vacua-a-consistent-perspective-for-superstrings-and-multi-fold-universes/), January 9, 2021.
- [16]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), "Quantum Gravity Asymptotic Safety from 2D Universal Regime and Smooth Transition to Dual Superstrings", [viXra:2208.0151v1, https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/02/07/quantum-gravity-asymptotic-safety-from-2d-universal-regime-and-smooth-transition-to-dual-superstrings/](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/02/07/quantum-gravity-asymptotic-safety-from-2d-universal-regime-and-smooth-transition-to-dual-superstrings/), January 29, 2021.
- [17]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "A Non-perturbative Proof of the Asymptotic Safety of 4D Einstein Gravity, With or Without Matter", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7953796>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/05/04/a-non-perturbative-proof-of-the-asymptotic-safety-of-4d-einstein-gravity-with-or-without-matter/>, May 4, 2022, [viXra:2305.0138](https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.0138).
- [18]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Dualities or Analogies between Superstrings and Multi-fold Universe", [viXra:2006.0178v1, https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/14/dualities-or-analogies-between-superstrings-and-multi-fold-universes/](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/14/dualities-or-analogies-between-superstrings-and-multi-fold-universes/), June 14, 2020.
- [19]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Alignments and Gaps Between Multi-fold Universes And Loop Quantum Gravity", [viXra:2006.0229v1, https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/19/multi-fold-universes-analysis-of-loop-quantum-gravity/](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/19/multi-fold-universes-analysis-of-loop-quantum-gravity/), June 18, 2020.
- [20]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Superstrings Encounter of the Second, Third or Fourth Types?", [viXra:2010.0140v1, https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/07/19/superstrings-encounter-of-the-second-third-or-fourth-types/](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/07/19/superstrings-encounter-of-the-second-third-or-fourth-types/), July 5, 2020.
- [21]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "Oops For The Loops II: Real Oops; LQG Does Not Optimize the Hilbert Einstein Action", [viXra:2301.0036v1, https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/01/05/oops-for-the-loops-ii-real-oops-lqg-does-not-optimize-the-hilbert-einstein-action/](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/01/05/oops-for-the-loops-ii-real-oops-lqg-does-not-optimize-the-hilbert-einstein-action/), January 5, 2022.
- [22]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), "What is the Multi-fold Theory? Its Main Characteristics in a Few Words", [vixra:2207.0172v1, https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/07/28/what-is-the-multi-fold-theory-its-main-characteristics-in-a-few-words/](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/07/28/what-is-the-multi-fold-theory-its-main-characteristics-in-a-few-words/), July 28, 2022.
- [23]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), "Justifying the Standard Model $U(1) \times SU(2) \times SU(3)$ Symmetry in a Multi-fold Universe", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8422911>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/08/08/justifyin-g-the-standard-model-u1-x-su2-x-su3-symmetry-in-a-multi-fold-universe/>, August 8, 2022, ([viXra:2310.0040v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.0040v1)).

- [24]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "The E/G conjecture: entanglement is gravity and gravity is entanglement", [viXra:2010.0139v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/10/15/the-e-g-conjecture-entanglement-is-gravity-and-gravity-is-entanglement/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/10/15/the-e-g-conjecture-entanglement-is-gravity-and-gravity-is-entanglement/>, October 15, 2020.
- [25]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Gravity-like Attractions and Fluctuations between Entangled Systems?", [viXra:2010.0010v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/25/gravity-like-attractions-and-fluctuations-between-entangled-systems/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/25/gravity-like-attractions-and-fluctuations-between-entangled-systems/>, June 24, 2020.
- [26]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Massless and Massive Multi-Gravity in a Multi-fold Universe", [viXra:2010.0095v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/30/massless-and-massive-multi-gravity-in-a-multi-fold-universe/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/30/massless-and-massive-multi-gravity-in-a-multi-fold-universe/>, June 19, 2020.
- [27]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Explaining Dark Energy, Small Cosmological Constant and Inflation Without New Physics?", [viXra:2006.0261v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/19/explaining-dark-energy-small-cosmological-constant-and-inflation-without-new-physics/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/19/explaining-dark-energy-small-cosmological-constant-and-inflation-without-new-physics/>, June 19, 2020.
- [28]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Ultimate Unification: Gravity-led Democracy vs. Uber-Symmetries", [viXra:2006.0211v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/16/ultimate-unification-gravity-led-democracy-vs-uber-symmetries/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/16/ultimate-unification-gravity-led-democracy-vs-uber-symmetries/>, June 16, 2020.
- [29]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), "Invalidation and Proof of the Mass Gap, and Viability of The Standard Model on a Discrete Spacetime", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8237456>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/07/15/invalidation-and-proof-of-the-mass-gap-and-viability-of-the-standard-model-on-a-discrete-spacetime/>, July 15, 2022. ([viXra:2308.0059](https://arxiv.org/abs/2308.0059)).
- [30]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), Stephane H. Maes, (2022), "A Conjecture: No Dark Matter will be discovered at LHC, or elsewhere", (v2), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8175806>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/07/08/a-prediction-no-dark-matter-will-be-discovered-at-lhc-or-elsewhere/>, July 8, 2022, [viXra:2307.0119](https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.0119).
- [31]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "Unruh effects, Hawking Black Hole Evaporation, Quantum Corrected Larmor Formula, Numbers of Particles in Curved Spacetime: "Same-Same, but Just A Bit Different"", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8306942>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/07/25/unruh-effects-hawking-black-hole-evaporation-quantum-corrected-larmor-formula-numbers-of-particles-in-curved-spacetime-same-same-but-just-a-bit-different/>, July 25, 2022, ([viXra:2309.0005](https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.0005)).
- [32]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Multi-fold Higgs Fields and Bosons", [viXra:2204.0146v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/11/10/multi-fold-higgs-fields-and-bosons/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/11/10/multi-fold-higgs-fields-and-bosons/>, November 6, 2020.
- [33]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Tracking Down The Standard Model With Gravity In Multi-Fold Universes", [viXra:2011.0208v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/08/30/tracking-down-the-standard-model-with-gravity-in-multi-fold-universes/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/08/30/tracking-down-the-standard-model-with-gravity-in-multi-fold-universes/>, August 20, 2020.
- [34]: Stephane H. Maes, (2020), "Particles of The Standard Model In Multi-Fold Universes", [viXra:2111.0071v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/11/05/particles-of-the-standard-model-in-multi-fold-universes/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/11/05/particles-of-the-standard-model-in-multi-fold-universes/>, November 4, 2020.
- [35]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), "Multi-fold Gravity-Electroweak Theory and Symmetry Breaking", [viXra:2211.0100](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/03/28/multi-fold-gravity-electroweak-theory-and-symmetry-breaking/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/03/28/multi-fold-gravity-electroweak-theory-and-symmetry-breaking/>, March 16, 2021.
- [36]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Viable Lattice Spacetime and Absence of Quantum Gravitational Anomalies in a Multi-fold Universe", [viXra:2205.0143v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/12/13/viable-lattice-spacetime-and-absence-of-quantum-gravitational-anomalies-in-a-multi-fold-universe/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/12/13/viable-lattice-spacetime-and-absence-of-quantum-gravitational-anomalies-in-a-multi-fold-universe/>, December 4, 2020.
- [37]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "Can Chirality Flips Occur in a Multi-Fold Universe? What About Conservation Laws? II", [viXra:2204.0152v2](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/08/20/can-chirality-flips-occur-in-a-), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/08/20/can-chirality-flips-occur-in-a->

[multi-fold-universe-what-about-conservation-laws-ii/](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/12/07/can-chirality-flips-occur-in-a-multi-fold-universe-what-about-conservation-laws/), August 20, 2022 and Stephane H Maes, (2020), “Can Chirality Flips Occur in a Multi-Fold Universe? What About Conservation Laws?”, [viXra:2204.0152](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/12/07/can-chirality-flips-occur-in-a-multi-fold-universe-what-about-conservation-laws/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/12/07/can-chirality-flips-occur-in-a-multi-fold-universe-what-about-conservation-laws/>, December 6, 2020.

[38]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), “Derivation of the Equivalence Principle in a Multi-fold Universe”, [viXra:2010.0090v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/29/derivation-of-the-equivalence-principle-in-a-multi-fold-universe/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/29/derivation-of-the-equivalence-principle-in-a-multi-fold-universe/>, June 19, 2020.

[39]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), “Progress on Proving the Mass gap for Yang Mills and Gravity (maybe it’s already proved...)”, [viXra:2006.0155v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/12/progresses-on-proving-the-mass-gap-for-yang-mills-and-gravity-maybe-its-already-proven/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/12/progresses-on-proving-the-mass-gap-for-yang-mills-and-gravity-maybe-its-already-proven/>, June 12, 2020.

[40]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), “Gravity Induced Anomalies Smearing in Standard Model so that Protons May Never Decay, Except in Black holes”, [viXra:2006.0128v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/13/gravity-induced-anomalies-smearing-in-standard-model-so-that-protons-may-never-decay-except-in-black-holes/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/13/gravity-induced-anomalies-smearing-in-standard-model-so-that-protons-may-never-decay-except-in-black-holes/>, June 13, 2020.

[41]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), “Gravity or Magnetic Monopoles? You Cannot Have Both! II”, [viXra:2006.0190v2](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/08/20/gravity-or-magnetic-monopoles-you-cannot-have-both-2/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/08/20/gravity-or-magnetic-monopoles-you-cannot-have-both-2/>, August 20, 2022; Stephane H Maes, (2020), “Gravity or Magnetic Monopoles? You Cannot Have Both!”, [viXra:2006.0190](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/15/gravity-or-magnetic-monopoles-you-cannot-have-both/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/15/gravity-or-magnetic-monopoles-you-cannot-have-both/>, June 15, 2020.

[42]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), “Right-handed neutrinos? Mass? Ask Gravity”, [viXra:2007.0018v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/21/right-handed-neutrinos-ask-gravity/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/21/right-handed-neutrinos-ask-gravity/>, June 23, 2020.

[43]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), “Strong CP Violation Tamed in The Presence of Gravity”, [viXra:2007.0025v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/23/strong-cp-violation-tamed-in-the-presence-of-gravity/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/23/strong-cp-violation-tamed-in-the-presence-of-gravity/>, June 21, 2020.

[44]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), “Gravity Dictates the Number of Fermion Generations: 3”, [viXra:2007.0068v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/24/gravity-dictates-the-number-of-fermion-generations-3/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/24/gravity-dictates-the-number-of-fermion-generations-3/>, June 24, 2020.

[45]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), “Gravity Stabilizes Electroweak Vacuum – No Bubble of Nothing to Worry About!”, [viXra:2007.0173v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/24/gravity-stabilizes-electroweak-vacuum-no-bubble-of-nothing-to-worry-about/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/24/gravity-stabilizes-electroweak-vacuum-no-bubble-of-nothing-to-worry-about/>, June 24, 2020.

[46]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), “More Matter Than Antimatter, All Falling Down”, [viXra:2010.0121v2](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/07/05/more-matter-than-antimatter-all-falling-down/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/07/05/more-matter-than-antimatter-all-falling-down/>, July 5, 2020. (V2: April 8, 2021).

[47]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), “No Conventional Sterile Neutrinos In a Multi-fold Universe: just SMG business as usual”, [viXra:2103.0202v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/10/02/no-conventional-sterile-neutrinos-in-a-multi-fold-universe-just-smg-business-as-usual/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/10/02/no-conventional-sterile-neutrinos-in-a-multi-fold-universe-just-smg-business-as-usual/>, October 1, 2020.

[48]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), “New Physics with LHCb to explain loss of lepton universality, or just gravity?”, [viXra:2103.0191v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/03/29/new-physics-with-lhcb-to-explain-loss-of-lepton-universality-or-just-gravity/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/03/29/new-physics-with-lhcb-to-explain-loss-of-lepton-universality-or-just-gravity/>, March 29, 2021.

[49]: Stephane H. Maes, “A bold prediction on the muon anomalous magnetic moment, and expected results to be published on April 7, 2021 by the Fermilab Muon g-2, and its explanation”, [viXra:2104.0030v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/04/01/a-bold-prediction-on-the-muon-anomalous-magnetic-moment-and-expected-results-to-be-published-on-april-7-2021-by-the-fermilab-muon-g-2-and-its-explanation/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/04/01/a-bold-prediction-on-the-muon-anomalous-magnetic-moment-and-expected-results-to-be-published-on-april-7-2021-by-the-fermilab-muon-g-2-and-its-explanation/>, April 1, 2021.

- [50]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), "New Physics is often not so new", [osf.io/z3sj6](https://zenodo.org/records/7791704), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/04/27/new-physics-is-often-not-so-new/>, April 27, 2021, <https://zenodo.org/records/7791704>.
- [51]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "Direction of Possible Multi-folds Corrections to the W Boson Mass", [osf.io/qvewa](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/04/08/direction-of-possible-multi-folds-corrections-to-the-w-boson-mass/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/04/08/direction-of-possible-multi-folds-corrections-to-the-w-boson-mass/>, April 8, 2022, [viXra:2304.0020](https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.0020).
- [52]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "Multi-folds in Yang Mills Feynman Diagrams", [osf.io/y8fpd](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/04/05/multi-folds-in-yang-mills-feynman-diagrams/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/04/05/multi-folds-in-yang-mills-feynman-diagrams/>, April 5, 2022, [viXra:2303.0161](https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.0161).
- [53]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), "Time-Varying Multi-fold Dark Energy Effects and Implications for the Hubble Tension", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10396357>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/11/13/time-varying-multi-fold-dark-energy-effects-and-implications-for-the-hubble-tension/>, November 13, 2022, <https://osf.io/preprints/osf/rxk8n>, [viXra:2312.0083v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.0083v1). Also as Stephane H. Maes, (2022), "The Possibility of a Multi-fold Time-Varying Hubble Constant", [viXra:2312.0083v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.0083v1).
- [54]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Explaining Dark Matter Without New Physics?", [viXra:2007.0006](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/21/explaining-dark-matter-without-new-physics/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/21/explaining-dark-matter-without-new-physics/>, June 21, 2020.
- [55]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Multi-Fold Universe Dark Matter Successful Explanation and the "Too Thin Universe" but "Too Strong Gravity Lensing by Galaxy Clusters"", [viXra:2102.0079v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/09/15/multi-fold-universe-dark-matter-successful-explanation-and-the-too-thin-universe-but-too-strong-gravity-lensing-by-galaxy-clusters/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/09/15/multi-fold-universe-dark-matter-successful-explanation-and-the-too-thin-universe-but-too-strong-gravity-lensing-by-galaxy-clusters/>, September 14, 2020.
- [56]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Multi-Fold Universe Dark Matter Effects Survive Low-Mass Galaxies with Dark Matter Deficits and Excesses", [viXra:2105.0042v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/10/14/multi-fold-universe-dark-matter-effects-survive-low-mass-galaxies-with-dark-matter-deficits-and-excesses/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/10/14/multi-fold-universe-dark-matter-effects-survive-low-mass-galaxies-with-dark-matter-deficits-and-excesses/>, October 14, 2020.
- [57]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Multi-Fold Dark Matter Effects and Early Supermassive Black Holes", [viXra:2105.0041v1](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/10/15/multi-fold-dark-matter-effects-and-early-supermassive-black-holes/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/10/15/multi-fold-dark-matter-effects-and-early-supermassive-black-holes/>, October 15, 2020.
- [58]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "Hints of Multi-fold Dark Matter Effects in the Universe", [osf.io/kw7g](https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/03/14/hints-of-multi-fold-dark-matter-effects-in-the-universe/), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/03/14/hints-of-multi-fold-dark-matter-effects-in-the-universe/>, March 14, 2022, <https://zenodo.org/record/7791678>.
- [59]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "Multi-fold Dark Matter and Energy Effects Fit The Ratios to Normal Matter in the Universe", <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10071554>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/08/14/multi-fold-dark-matter-and-energy-effects-fit-the-ratios-to-normal-matter-in-the-universe/>, August 14, 2022, (<https://osf.io/mahsu>, [viXra:2311.0018v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.0018v1)).
- [60]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), "Explaining Imbalance of Tidally Ejected Stars from Open Stars Clusters Without MOND", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10421124>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/11/19/explaining-imbalance-of-tidally-ejected-stars-from-open-stars-clusters-without-mond/>, November 19, 2022, <https://osf.io/bp64c>.
- [61]: Physics Stack Exchange, (2019), "Why does the Higgs boson have electroweak charges T_3 and Y_w but does not have an antiparticle with opposite charges?", <https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/494409/why-does-the-higgs-boson-have-electroweak-charges-t-3-and-y-w-but-does-n>, July 31, 2019.
- [62]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "Multi-fold Discrete Fractal Spacetime, and the Viability of Local vs. Non-Local Hidden Variables", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10344634>,

<https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/10/30/multi-fold-discrete-fractal-spacetime-and-the-viability-of-local-vs-non-local-hidden-variable-viability/>, October 30, 2022, osf.io/qevys, [viXra:2312.0065v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.0065v1).

[63]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), "Right-handed Neutrinos and Traversable Wormholes: the key to entanglement, gravity and multi-folds extensions to ER=EPR?", [viXra:2211.0173v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.0173v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/04/03/right-handed-neutrinos-and-traversable-wormholes-the-key-to-entanglement-gravity-and-multi-folds-extensions-to-erepr/>, April 3, 2021.

[64]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), "Spacetime and Gravity are 2D around Planck Scales: A Universal Property of Consistent Quantum Gravity", [viXra:2211.0001v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.0001v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/03/23/spacetime-and-gravity-are-2d-around-planck-scales-a-universal-property-of-consistent-quantum-gravity/>, March 20, 2021.

[65]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), "Multi-fold Non-Commutative Spacetime, Higgs and The Standard Model with Gravity", [viXra:2212.0037v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2212.0037v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/04/18/multi-fold-non-commutative-spacetime-higgs-and-the-standard-model-with-gravity/>, April 11, 2021.

[66]: Katie McCormick, (2022), "Asymmetry Detected in the Distribution of Galaxies. Two new studies suggest that certain tetrahedral arrangements of galaxies outnumber their mirror images, potentially reflecting details of the universe's birth. But confirmation is needed.", <https://www.quantamagazine.org/asymmetry-detected-in-the-distribution-of-galaxies-20221205/>. Retrieved on December 5, 2022.

[67]: Oliver H. E. Philcox, (2022), "Probing Parity-Violation with the Four-Point Correlation Function of BOSS Galaxies", [arXiv:2206.04227v2](https://arxiv.org/abs/2206.04227v2).

[68]: Jiamin Hou, Zachary Slepian, Robert N. Cahn, (2022), "Measurement of Parity-Odd Modes in the Large-Scale 4-Point Correlation Function of SDSS BOSS DR12 CMASS and LOWZ Galaxies", [arXiv:2206.03625v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2206.03625v1).

[69]: Arthur Lue, Limin Wang, Marc Kamionkowski, (1998-1999), "Cosmological Signature of New Parity-Violating Interactions", [astro-ph/9812088v2](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/9812088v2).

[70]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Multi-fold Gravitons In-N-Out Spacetime", [viXra:2010.0155v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2010.0155v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/07/27/multi-fold-gravitons-in-n-out-spacetime/>, July 27, 2020, (posted September 6, 2020)

[71]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "Gravitational Bootstrap, S-matrix, Superstrings, and The Plausible Unphysicality of Gravitons", [viXra:2301.0155v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.0155v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/02/06/gravitational-bootstrap-s-matrix-superstrings-and-the-plausible-unphysicality-of-gravitons/>, February 6, 2022.

[72]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "The Replica Trick, Wormholes, Island formula, and Quantum Extremal Surfaces, and How the AdS/CFT Correspondence Conjecture, and Hence the M-theory, Encounters Multi-folds", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207057>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/09/20/the-replica-trick-its-wormholes-islands-and-quantum-extremal-surfaces-and-how-the-ads-cft-correspondence-conjecture-and-hence-the-m-theory-encounters-multi-folds/>, September 26, 2022, (osf.io/xwf6q/). Also published as: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "The Replica Trick, Wormholes, Island formula, and Quantum Extremal Surfaces", September 26, 2022 ([viXra:2311.0154v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.0154v1)).

[73]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Particles, Especially Virtual Particles, in a Multi-fold Universe vs. QFT", [viXra:2010.0133v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2010.0133v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/07/11/particles-especially-virtual-particles-in-a-multi-fold-universe-vs-qft/>, July 10, 2020.

[74]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Comments to "Yes, Stephen Hawking Lied To Us All About How Black Holes Decay"", <https://osf.io/v7thb/>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/07/11/comments-to-yes-stephen-hawking-lied-to-us-all-about-how-black-holes-decay/>, July 11, 2020.

[75]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Different approaches to compute Hawking Black Holes Decay", [viXra:2208.0009v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2208.0009v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/different-approaches-to-compute-hawking-black-holes-decay/>, August 1, 2022. (Originally published July 11, 2020).

- [76]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Multi-Fold Black Holes: Entropy, Evolution and Quantum Extrema", [viXra:2105.0136v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2105.0136v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/11/01/multi-fold-black-holes-entropy-evolution-and-quantum-extrema/>, October 31, 2020.
- [77]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "No Gravity Shield in Multi-folds Universes", [viXra:2010.0032v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2010.0032v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/26/no-gravity-shields-in-multi-folds-universes/>, June 26, 2020.
- [78]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Area Laws Between Multi-Fold Universes and AdS", [viXra:2010.0207v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2010.0207v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/08/10/area-laws-between-multi-fold-universes-and-ads/>, August 10, 2020.
- [79]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "Trans-Planckian Censorship Conjecture: Factual in Multi-fold Universes as well as GR Universes", [viXra:2303.0025v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.0025v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/03/13/trans-planckian-censorship-conjecture-factual-in-multi-fold-universes-as-well-as-gr-universes/>, March 12, 2022.
- [80]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), "Multi-fold Embeddings, Space Time Matter Induction or Gravity Asymptotically Safe and The AdS/CFT Correspondence Conjecture, they all can recover the Standard Model", [viXra:2212.0120v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2212.0120v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/12/20/multi-fold-embeddings-space-time-matter-induction-or-gravity-asymptotically-safe-and-the-ads-cft-correspondence-conjecture-they-all-can-recover-the-standard-model-or-smg/>, December 20, 2021.
- [81]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), "Comments on radiation black hole simulation on a lattice", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/07/25/unruh-effects-hawking-black-hole-evaporation-quantum-corrected-larmor-formula-numbers-of-particles-in-curved-spacetime-same-same-but-just-a-bit-different/#comment-5099>, December 2, 2022.
- [82]: Stephane H. Maes, (2021), "Neutrons are forming an external skin in Nuclei and Neutron Stars", <https://shmaes.wordpress.com/2021/05/08/neutrons-are-forming-an-external-skin-in-nuclei-and-neutron-stars/>, May 8, 2021.
- [83]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "The Yang Mills Double Copy leads to New AdS/CFT + Gravity Correspondences, or How the M-theory encounters Multi-fold Universes", v1.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7827248>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/04/22/the-yang-mills-double-copy-leads-to-new-ads-cft-gravity-correspondences-or-how-the-m-theory-encounters-multi-fold-universes/>, April 22, 2022. (v1: at [zenodo.7827249](https://zenodo.org/record/7827249)).
- [84]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), "Schwinger effect and charged black holes", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/11/01/multi-fold-black-holes-entropy-evolution-and-quantum-extrema/#comment-4686>, September 25, 2022.
- [85]: Stephane H. Maes, "Comments on asymmetry of distributions of ejected star from gas clusters", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/21/explaining-dark-matter-without-new-physics/#comment-4813> and subsequent comments, October 27, 2022
- [86]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), "Comments on Multi-fold mechanisms as Hermitian vs. Unitary processes", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/25/gravity-like-attractions-and-fluctuations-between-entangled-systems/#comment-4359>, July 27, 2022.
- [87]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "The W-type Multi-Fold Hypothesis and Quantum Physics Interpretation of wave Functions and QFT", [viXra:2207.0118v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.0118v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/12/24/the-w-type-multi-fold-hypothesis-and-quantum-physics-interpretation-of-wave-functions-and-qft/>, December 20, 2020.
- [88]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Implicit Multi-Fold Mechanisms in a Neural Network Model of the Universe", [viXra:2012.0191v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2012.0191v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/09/12/implicit-multi-fold-mechanisms-in-a-neural-network-model-of-the-universe/>, September 12, 2020.

- [89]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Interpretation of "Neural Network as the World"", [viXra:2012.0197v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2012.0197v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/09/14/interpretation-of-neural-network-as-the-world/>, September 14, 2020.
- [90]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Entangled Neural Networks from Multi-fold Universes to Biology", [viXra:2207.0174v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.0174v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/12/31/entangled-neural-networks-from-multi-fold-universes-to-biology/>, December 25, 2020.
- [91]: Wikipedia, "Lambda-CDM model", https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lambda-CDM_model. Retrieved on August 14, 2022.
- [92]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "No Gravity Induced Wave Function Collapse in a Multi-fold Universe", [viXra:2012.0152v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2012.0152v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/09/11/no-gravity-induced-wave-function-collapse-in-a-multi-fold-universe/>, September 11, 2020. Also as: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "No Gravity Superposition Induced Wave Function Collapse in a Multi-fold Universe", [viXra:2012.0152v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2012.0152v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/09/11/no-gravity-induced-wave-function-collapse-in-a-multi-fold-universe/>, September 11, 2020.
- [93]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), ""Quantum Gravity Emergence from Entanglement in a Multi-Fold Universe": 2D or 2+1D spacetime at small scales", [viXra:2103.0142](https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.0142), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/03/20/quantum-gravity-emergence-from-entanglement-in-a-multi-fold-universe-2d-or-21d-spacetime-at-small-scales/>, March 20, 2021.
- [94]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), "CO₂ and CH₄ absorption powered by nuclear fusion, via fission, is the only way to manage climate change and the Planet's trigger points", [viXra:2211.0154v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.0154v1), <https://shmaes.wordpress.com/2022/04/09/co2-and-ch4-absorption-powered-fission-is-the-only-way-to-manage-climate-change-and-the-planets-trigger-points/>, April 9, 2022.
- [95]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), "Oops For The Loops: Mounting LQG Woes And A Challenge To The LQG Community", [viXra:2212.0168](https://arxiv.org/abs/2212.0168), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/12/30/oops-for-loops-mounting-lqg-woes-and-a-challenge-to-the-lqg-community/>, December 29, 2021.
- [96]: Stephane H. Maes, (2021-2022), "Our universe is 4D", Comments and following comments at <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/09/19/renormalization-and-asymptotic-safety-of-gravity-in-a-multi-fold-universe-more-tracking-of-the-standard-model-at-the-cost-of-supersymmetries-guts-and-superstrings/#comment-1416>. January 16, 2021 and after.
- [97]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), "Multi-fold gravity and double copy of gauge theory", osf.io/xun82, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/05/04/multi-fold-gravity-and-double-copy-of-gauge-theory/>, May 4, 2021, [viXra:2303.0114](https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.0114).
- [98]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), "Entanglement Concretizes Time in a Multi-fold Universe", [viXra:2010.0083v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2010.0083v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/28/entanglement-concretizes-time-in-a-multi-fold-universe/>, June 28, 2020.
- [99]: Stephane H Maes, (2021), "How the ER = EPR, GR = QM and AdS/CFT correspondence conjectures, can be explained in multi-fold theory, along with the E/G conjecture. A call to the Physics Community!", [viXra:2111.0144v2](https://arxiv.org/abs/2111.0144v2), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/11/28/how-the-er-epr-gr-qm-and-ads-cft-correspondence-conjectures-can-be-explained-in-multi-fold-theory-and-the-e-g-conjecture-explains-and-realize-in-a-multi-fold-universe-a-call-to-the-physics-comm/>, December 28, 2021.

[100]: Stephane H Maes, (2020), “A Multi-fold Universe Genesis Inspired By Explosive Total Collision: The Source Of The Big Bang?”, [viXra:2208.0082v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/2208.0082v1), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/01/17/a-multi-fold-universe-genesis-inspired-by-total-explosion-collision-the-source-of-the-big-bang/>, January 12, 2021.

[101]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), “JWST and the Big Bang invalidation”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/01/17/a-multi-fold-universe-genesis-inspired-by-total-explosion-collision-the-source-of-the-big-bang/#comment-4577>, and following comments. August 21, 2022.

[102]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), “Schwinger effect dominates near the horizon of charged black holes near extremality and reduces the charge”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/07/25/unruh-effects-hawking-black-hole-evaporation-quantum-corrected-larmor-formula-numbers-of-particles-in-curved-spacetime-same-same-but-just-a-bit-different/#comment-4687>, September 23, 2022.

[103] Stephane H Maes, (2022), “Charm of the proton”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/03/29/new-physics-with-lhcb-to-explain-loss-of-lepton-universality-or-just-gravity/#comment-3791>, March 27, 2022.

[104]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022-2023), “Confusing mathematical duality to predict quantum computing algorithm, with building a wormhole”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/10/11/circular-arguments-in-string-and-superstring-theory-from-a-multi-fold-universe-perspective/comment-page-1/#comment-5093>, and following related comments, November 30, 2022.

[105]: Stephane H. Maes, {2022}, “Black holes effects outside the black holes do not mean that Hawking radiation is not occurring at its horizon”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/different-approaches-to-compute-hawking-black-holes-decay/#comment-5027>, November 23, 2022.

[106]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), “A Better Quantum Extremal Surface and Island Interpretation that explains the Associated Massive Gravity”, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10437116>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/12/03/a-better-quantum-extremal-surface-and-island-interpretation-that-explains-the-associated-massive-gravity/>, December 3, 2022, (<https://osf.io/dn3kh>).

References added on December 29, 2023

[107]: Stephane H Maes, (2022), “2D Random Walks of Massless Higgs Bosons as Microscopic Interpretation of the Asymptotic Safety of Gravity, and of the Standard Model”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/12/28/2d-random-walks-of-massless-higgs-bosons-as-microscopic-interpretation-of-the-asymptotic-safety-of-gravity-and-of-the-standard-model/>, December 28, 2022.

[108]: Stephane H. Maes, (2022), “Multi-folds, Non-Commutative Spacetime, Spin, and All That”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/12/31/the-principles-of-quantum-mechanics/>, December 31, 2022.

[109]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), “Yeah or Nay on Black Holes as Explanation for Dark Energy?”, osf.io/369pd, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/03/01/yeah-or-nay-on-black-holes-as-explanation-for-dark-energy/>, V3, March 26, 2023. (V2: March 12, 2023, V1: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), “Yeah or Nay on Black Holes as Explanation for Dark Energy?”, [viXra:2303.0031](https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.0031), <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/03/01/yeah-or-nay-on-black-holes-as-explanation-for-dark-energy/>, March 1, 2023).

[110]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), “Dynamic sources, Dynamic Multi-folds, and General Relativity Lense-Thirring and Frame Dragging Effects”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/03/12/dynamic-sources-dynamic-multi-folds-and-general-relativity-lens-thirring-and-frame-dragging-effects/>, March 12, 2023.

[111]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), “The Multi-fold Least Action Principle, a Quasi Theory Of Everything”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/02/19/the-multi-fold-least-action-principle-a-quasi-theory-of-everything/>, February 19, 2023.

- [112]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "Maybe, black holes do not systematically decohere quantum states", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/11/01/multi-fold-black-holes-entropy-evolution-and-quantum-extrema/#comment-6315>, March 7, 2023.
- [113]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "No electroweak / Higgs mass hierarchy problem in multi-fold theory", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/03/28/multi-fold-gravity-electroweak-theory-and-symmetry-breaking/#comment-6794>, March 30, 2023.
- [114]: Stephane H. Maes, "Right-handed neutrinos in the multi-fold stabilize the multi-fold unconstrained KK space time matter induction and scattering", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/04/03/right-handed-neutrinos-and-traversable-wormholes-the-key-to-entanglement-gravity-and-multi-folds-extensions-to-erepr/comment-page-1/#comment-6875>, April 8, 2023.
- [115]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "No lack of clumpiness, just as needed", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/21/explaining-dark-matter-without-new-physics/comment-page-1/#comment-6974>. April 12, 2023.
- [116]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "Multi-fold Universes, Multiverses and Many Worlds", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/04/08/multi-fold-universes-multi-folds-and-many-worlds/>, April 8, 2023.
- [117]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "Comment on black hole decoherence", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/11/01/multi-fold-black-holes-entropy-evolution-and-quantum-extrema/#comment-6315>, March 7, 2023.
- [118]: Stephane H Maes, (2023), "Comments of the universe is too smooth", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/21/explaining-dark-matter-without-new-physics/#comment-6086>, February 9, 2023, and <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/21/explaining-dark-matter-without-new-physics/#comment-6974>, April 12, 2023.
- [119]: Stephane H Maes, (2023), "Our real universe is macroscopically 4D. Hints come from every direction & show that it had to be so", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/04/23/our-real-universe-is-macroscopically-4d-hints-come-from-every-directions-show-that-it-had-to-be-so/>, April 23, 2023.
- [120]: Stephane H Maes, (2023), "No Gravitational Evaporation of Everything à la Schwinger, only for Black Holes", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/07/15/no-gravitational-evaporation-of-everything-a-la-schwinger-only-for-black-holes/>, July 15, 2023.
- [121]: Stephane H Maes, (2023), "Unstable QFT and SM with Gravity except in a Multi-fold Universe", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/07/19/unstable-qft-and-sm-with-gravity-except-in-a-multi-fold-universe/>, July 19, 2023.
- [122]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "Comments about massive galaxies without dark matter", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/10/14/multi-fold-universe-dark-matter-effects-survive-low-mass-galaxies-with-dark-matter-deficits-and-excesses/#comment-7430>, July 20, 2023.
- [123]: Stephane H Maes, (2023), "Less Cracks in the Standard Cosmology in a Multi-fold Universe with its Quantum Random walks", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/06/20/less-cracks-in-the-standard-cosmology-in-a-multi-fold-universe-with-its-quantum-random-walks/>, June 19, 2023.
- [124]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "Ad Astra With Warp Drives? Probably Not", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/12/09/ad-astra-longe-with-warp-drives-probably-not/>, December 9, 2023.

- [125]: Stephane H Maes, (2023), "2D gravity and 2D Yang Mills Physics is all what matters", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/04/23/our-real-universe-is-macroscopically-4d-hints-come-from-every-directions-show-that-it-had-to-be-so/comment-page-1/#comment-7588>, August 5, 2023.
- [126]: Stephane H Maes (2023), "The Multi-fold Theory – Draft Raw Compendium of Research Papers (till August, 2023)", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242021>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/08/12/the-multi-fold-theory-draft-raw-compendium-of-research-papers-till-august-2023/>, August 12, 2023. (<https://osf.io/swqmb>).
- [127]: Stephane H Maes, (2023), "Barnett's resolution of the Minkowski – Abraham dilemma holds, no 4-vector issue", <https://shmaes.wordpress.com/2023/08/11/barnetts-resolution-of-the-minkowski-abraham-dilemma-holds-no-4-vector-issue/>, August 13, 2023.
- [128]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "Persisting on No Decoherence due to Gravity, Black Holes, or Spacetime Curvature Superpositions", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/08/18/persisting-on-no-decoherence-due-to-gravity-black-holes-or-spacetime-curvature-superpositions/>, August 18, 2023.
- [129]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "No supersymmetry at $D \leq 4$ with a positive cosmological constant", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/07/08/a-prediction-no-dark-matter-will-be-discovered-at-lhc-or-elsewhere/#comment-7563>. July 23, 2023.
- [130]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "The universe is exactly the only thing that it could be if it is a 4D multi-fold universe! No fine-tuning problem, no invocation of God or multiverses", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/04/08/multi-fold-universes-multi-folds-and-many-worlds/comment-page-1/#comment-8037>, October 7, 2023.
- [131]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "Justification for the multi-fold mappings, and dynamic multi-fold mechanism", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/12/24/the-w-type-multi-fold-hypothesis-and-quantum-physics-interpretation-of-wave-functions-and-qft/comment-page-1/#comment-8092>, October 29, 2023.
- [132]: Stephane H. Maes, (2020-2023), "Quantum Gravity Emergence from Entanglement in a Multi-Fold Universe – V3: Update to section 4.1 – Multi-folds for Entanglement and EPR", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/quantum-gravity-emergence-from-entanglement-in-a-multi-fold-universe-v3-update-to-section-4-1-multi-folds-for-entanglement-and-epr/>.
- [133]: Stephane H. Maes, (2020-2023), "Quantum Gravity Emergence from Entanglement in a Multi-Fold Universe", V3, <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7792911>, October 29, 2023.
- [134]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "Path integrals and wormholes impact on the cosmological constant", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/09/20/the-replica-trick-its-wormholes-islands-and-quantum-extremal-surfaces-and-how-the-ads-cft-correspondence-conjecture-and-hence-the-m-theory-encounters-multi-folds/comment-page-1/#comment-7978>, September 3, 2023.
- [135]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "Microscopic interpretation of mass acquisition from massless Higgs bosons", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/02/28/more-on-multi-fold-particles-as-microscopic-black-holes-with-higgs-regularizing-extremality-and-singularities/#comment-8412>, November 5, 2023.
- [136]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "Justifying the Multi-folds Mechanisms, Mapping, Tenancy and More", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/11/10/justifying-the-multi-folds-mechanisms-mapping-tenancy-and-more/>, November 10, 2023.
- [137]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), "In multi-fold theory, the expansion of the universe is not a mirage", <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/19/explaining-dark-energy-small-cosmological-constant-and-inflation-without-new-physics/#comment-7242>, June 20, 2023.

- [138]: Stephane H. Maes, “Multi-fold dark energy is also a fluctuation of quantum vacuum fluctuations”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/06/19/explaining-dark-energy-small-cosmological-constant-and-inflation-without-new-physics/#comment-6111>, February 18, 2023.
- [139]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), “No supersymmetry”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/11/21/no-supersymmetry/>, November 21, 2023.
- [140]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), “It’s experimentally validated: antimatter falls down, no antigravity”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2020/07/05/more-matter-than-antimatter-all-falling-down/#comment-8018> and subsequent comments, September 27, 2023.
- [141]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), “Particle internal symmetries and anti-particles when modeled as microscopic black holes or random walk patterns”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2021/02/28/more-on-multi-fold-particles-as-microscopic-black-holes-with-higgs-regularizing-extremality-and-singularities/#comment-8634>, November 28, 2023.
- [142]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), “Information has no mass”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/12/14/information-has-no-mass/>, December 14, 2023
- [143]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), “Gravity is Quantum”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/12/19/gravity-is-quantum/>, December 19, 2023.
- [144]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), “Multi-folds for Entanglement and EPR”, <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10059877>, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/11/01/multi-folds-for-entanglement-and-epr/> October 29, 2023, (viXra:2311.0001v1), also as “Update to section 4.1 of “Quantum Gravity Emergence from Entanglement in a Multi-Fold Universe” – Multi-folds for Entanglement and EPR”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2023/10/29/update-to-section-4-1-of-quantum-gravity-emergence-from-entanglement-in-a-multi-fold-universe-multi-folds-for-entanglement-and-epr/>, (<https://osf.io/54ycm/>).
- [145]: Stephane H. Maes, (2023), “A Fractal spacetime just leads to rescaled cosmological constant. Yet that may provide a time varying effect”, <https://shmaesphysics.wordpress.com/2022/10/30/multi-fold-discrete-fractal-spacetime-and-the-viability-of-local-vs-non-local-hidden-variable-viability/comment-page-1/#comment-8896>. December 14, 2023.
- [146]: Wikipedia, “Weak interaction”, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Weak_interaction. Retrieved for this paper on December 29, 2023.